

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AGYEMANG****FIRST NAME: NANA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (MSWord Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. From the answers below, choose the sentence that is correctly punctuated.

- The creative writer, Jay Jay lived a long life.
- The creative writer Jay Jay, lived a long life.
- The creative writer Jay Jay lived a long life.¹**
- The creative writer Jay, Jay lived a long life.

2. Choose the answer that best describes an in-text citation of a dissertation.

- (Agyemang 2024, 13).²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 19.

² Kate L. Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*,

- (Agyemang, Nana 2024, 13).
- (Nana Agyemang 2024, 13).
- (Agyemang. 2024, 13).

3. Choose from the answers below the best in-text citation of the EUCLID Coursepack.

- A. (EUCLID 2021, 17)
- B. (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 17)
- C. (EUCLID 2021, 17) or (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 17)
- D. None of the above

- A only.
- B only.
- C only.³
- D only.

4. Which of the following initial parts of a dissertation is the first opportunity for the researcher to present the purpose to the reader?

- Abstract.
- Table of contents.
- Dedication.

Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers, Ninth Edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 202.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 2.

Title.⁴

5. Which is the most effective way to avoid plagiarism?

Creatively rewrite a quote without citing the source.

Appropriately cite the author or source of the quote.⁵

Creatively rewrite a quote and include the source.

Appropriately use the exact quote without citing the source.

6. Which of the following is the most acceptable way to cite a decision of the Court of Justice of the European Union?

According to *Karl Heinz Bablok v Freistaat Bayern*, the court points out in paragraph 5 of its judgment that...⁶

In *Karl Heinz Bablok v Freistaat Bayern*, the court points out in paragraph 5 that...

In *Karl Heinz Bablok v Freistaat Bayern*, the court points out that...

According to *Karl Heinz Bablok v Freistaat Bayern*, the court points out in its judgment that...

7. Which is the wrong way to cite a journal article in a bibliography?

⁴ James P. Sampson. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

⁶ European Commission. *A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition (Luxembourg: European Commission, 2021), 91.

- Taylor, Quentin. “The mask of Publius: Alexander Hamilton and the politics of Expediency.” *American Political Thoughts* 5, no. 1 (Winter 2016): 55-79 <https://doi.org/10.1086/684559>.
- Quentin Taylor “The mask of Publius: Alexander Hamilton and the politics of Expediency.” *American Political Thoughts* 5, no. 1 (Winter 2016): 55-79 <https://doi.org/10.1086/684559>.⁷**
- Taylor, Quentin, and Nana Agyemang “The mask of Publius: Alexander Hamilton and the politics of Expediency.” *American Political Thoughts* 5, no. 1 (Winter 2016): 55-79 <https://doi.org/10.1086/684559>.
- Taylor, Quentin. “The mask of Publius: Alexander Hamilton and the politics of Expediency.” *American Political Thoughts* 5, no. 1 (Winter 2016): 55 <https://doi.org/10.1086/684559>.

8. The sources of all the statements below must be cited except:

- Economic globalization is changing state sovereignty.
- Smoking causes lung cancer.⁸**
- The unemployment rate of Hispanics is at an all-time low of 5%.
- Two out of five deaths among U.S. teens are the result of a motor vehicle crash.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 190.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 37.

9. Which of the following is not a component of dissertation research?

- The dissertation concept paper.
- The dissertation.
- The manuscript
- Abstract.**⁹

10. All the following are primary legislation of the European Union except:

- EU Treaty.
- Euratom treaty.
- Treaty on the Function of the European Union.
- Directive 2013/32/EU.**¹⁰

⁹ James P. Sampson. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 9.

¹⁰ European Commission. *A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition (Luxembourg: European Commission, 2021), 74-75.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Sampson, James P. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

European Commission. *A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition. Luxembourg: European Commission, 2021.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.